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Learning Media of Sundanese Traditional Games in Early Childhood Education

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the views of teachers, principals, and school owners regarding the urgency of utilizing the richness of traditional Sundanese games as learning media for early childhood education, as well as their implementation in the curriculum. It also analyzes and synthesizes various learning media based on traditional Sundanese games developed by teachers, which are relevant for learning in early childhood for 4 to 6 years. The quantitative descriptive method is used to answer the problem formulation regarding the urgency and implementation of children's traditional games as learning media for Early Childhood Education (ECE). Data were collected by indirect interviews using a questionnaire tested for validity and reliability. The result showed that the teachers, principals, and school owners value the use of traditional games in ECE learning. These games are important to be explored and used as learning media to improve and strengthen students' character. Furthermore, it is remarkable that some teachers have also created new games based on existing traditional games.

Keywords: Early Childhood Education, Learning Media, Sundanese Traditional Games

1. Introduction

Early childhood is a golden age when children begin and are highly sensitive to environmental stimuli. The sensitive period is when physical and psychological functions are mature enough to respond to environmental stimuli. Therefore, the environment should be conditioned to support the exploration of sensory, motor, cognition, language, social, psychological, and religious values positively and optimally. (Bergen, 2002; Werker & Hensch, 2015; Renfree & Fox, 2017; Ardoin, N.M., Bowers, A.W. (2020).

The first and foremost environment is the family. The natural parenting pattern of the family, which is the first environment, greatly determines the stages and conditions of optimizing the children's growth and development. Early Childhood Education (ECE), as the next environment, has a strategic position and is very important in supporting the growth and development of early childhood. Therefore, ECE schools need to be conditioned and

developed to have quality curricula, teachers, counseling services, learning processes, and educational facilities (Nafisa, Barliana, Rahmannullah, 2022; Chapman, O’Gorman, 2022).

In the Indonesian context, several problems are faced by early childhood education. One of the problems is that the majority of ECE learning is still focused on academic reading and writing instead of developing attitudes and character. On the other hand, the rapid and massive development of information technology has entered the family room. In many busy families, or lack of education, or lack of understanding, and sensitivity, some early childhood children are exposed to the negative impacts of these technology and information media. Similarly, most modern games for early childhood do not provide adequate stimulation for healthy growth and development.

Amid information globalization, foreign cultural pressures, electronic, and online games, it is important to introduce local context, place identity, and local cultural roots to children from an early age. Traditional games can be an effective vehicle to support these efforts (Gipit, et al., 2017; Pyae, A. 2018). This is consistent with the view of Zaini (2016) that traditional games, which are now widely abandoned, show extraordinary wealth and wisdom for the growth and development of early childhood.

Local wisdom as a cultural heritage should continue to be explored. Excavating cultural roots and local wisdom is important to gain knowledge about the content of values, cultural patterns, and characteristics of traditional games. This exploration is not only in the context of heritage preservation and learning but is also adopted creatively to develop contemporary culture (Barliana & Cahyani, 2014). This includes adopting values, patterns, and characteristics of traditional Sundanese games to develop an early childhood-friendly school curriculum.

Based on this background, this study has two objectives. First, it describes the view on the urgency of utilizing traditional Sundanese games as a medium of ECE learning, as well as its implementation in the curriculum, which is limited to aspects of the Syllabus and Learning Program Plans (LPP) or Daily Activity Plans (DAP). Second, it analyzes and synthesizes various learning media based on traditional Sundanese games developed by teachers and relevant for learning in early childhood for 4 to 6 years.

Early childhood is an important period of human development of multiple intelligences. It is a period of exploring various interests, as well as the ability to adapt to the surrounding environment (Watson, 2016; Fadlillah, M., et al., 2020). The environment has a significant effect on the mental and behavior of a child. The instantaneous reception of all environmental information and stimuli significantly impacts children’s lives (Laurens, 2004; Diyanti, Amiuza, Mustikawati, 2014).

Generally, society views early childhood as a period of passivity, fantasy, and play that is disconnected from knowledge and understanding of the world and its environment. It should also be seen as an early period of active involvement in developing cognitive abilities, which are children’s capacity to think more complexly and to reason and solve problems. Developing these cognitive abilities will make it easier for children to master broader general knowledge and function naturally in their everyday lives (Novitasari, 2018). Cognitive development is a concern because it relates to skills, memory, language, and problem-solving abilities (Retnaningrum, 2016).

Continuing cognitive development and interaction with the world, children learn to utilize more ordered reasoning, characterized by a more logical, flexible, and structured thought process. Piaget argues that from the age of a toddler, a person has a certain ability to deal with the objects around him. This ability is still very simple, consisting of motor sensor abilities. Children actively understand their world using schema, assimilation, accommodation, organization, and balance. This ability enables them to explore and make their environment the basis for knowledge about the world they will acquire later, evolving into more advanced and complex abilities.

The phases of cognitive development show how understanding, processing information, problem-solving, and knowledge vary over the course of a person’s life. These stages are sensorimotor (0–2 years), preoperational (2–7 years), concrete (7–11 years), and formal (11–15 years). Children actively use schema, assimilation, accommodation, organization, and balance to understand the world. Their knowledge is formed gradually in line with the experience of the information encountered, and they experience a definite sequence of cognitive

development stages. At each stage, both the quantity and quality of the children's abilities showed improvement (Piaget, 1957; Wadsworth, 2004).

Based on the theory of child development, the Basic Framework for Curriculum 2013 for Early Childhood Education (Yusuf, 2018) stipulates some principles for implementing early childhood education. They include being oriented to Children's needs, learning through play, a conducive environment, using integrated learning, developing various life skills, the use of educational media and learning resources, as well as graduation implementation and repetition. Likewise, the curriculum is developed philosophically on the basis that education is rooted in the nation's culture to build its present and future life. Furthermore, students are the inheritors of the nation's creative culture and are active learners with the talent to learn various things around them. The educational process requires exemplary and continuous protection, and learning activities are carried out through play.

Traditional games can stimulate children to develop cooperation, and adjustment, interact positively with each other, condition children in self-control, develop empathy for friends, obey rules, and respect others. Subsequently, Huizinga (1971) stated that traditional games are carried out to instill culture and character in the perpetrators. This character culture occurs directly or indirectly, such as unyielding character and sportsmanship.

Gelisli and Yazici (2015) revealed that playing is one of the children's basic needs. They combine all the knowledge and skills needed in the future through play and are able to explain themselves and demonstrate their skills. Furthermore, traditional games are closely related to the 90s era when children developed without the influence of technology. They still think that various aspects of life are simple, including realizing the importance of local wisdom.

Traditional games are one part that can be reintroduced into the field of childhood education, thereby reinforcing cultural and character education values. According to Zaini (2016), a founder of the Hong community, traditional games can be interpreted as a fun activity carried out according to tradition, which creates a sense of satisfaction for the perpetrators. They have been known since ancient times and have high cultural and traditional elements. In general, it has a high philosophical value and positive properties for developing the child's personality. Traditional dominant games involve relatively many players or are communally oriented. Unsurprisingly, almost every folk game has a very large number of members. This is because, in addition to prioritizing the shared joy factor, the game has a deeper purpose of deepening interaction skills between players (interpersonal potential).

Learning media such as traditional games have many benefits and positive values compared to modern. The element of togetherness is essential in various kinds of traditional games, aiming to foster a sense of mutual cooperation. The togetherness that has been grown with children's games can train a sense of caring between others. Traditional games are full of noble values and norms useful for children to understand and find balance in the order of life. Furthermore, the games also build physical activeness, which positively affects health (Pranoto, Sugiyono, and Hong, 2014).

Traditional games have their characteristics, and they tend to use objects around without buying them. This is carried out with great imagination and creativity because the players should be able to interpret, imagine, and utilize several objects used in playing as they wish. Based on the description and definition above, it can be said that traditional games involve abilities and culture (Parlebas, 2010; Ambretti, Palumbo, Kourkoutas, 2019). Hence, they have no negative influence on the children.

Traditional games involve an informal learning process and create an atmosphere that can stimulate students to learn and master skills. Furthermore, children make choices, solve problems, communicate, and negotiate in their play. They create imaginary events and exercise physical, social, and cognitive skills. The game is able to provide an element of education to children at a low cost and with satisfying results. They are full of moral-ethical values and the culture of the supporting community. Furthermore, traditional or folk games prioritize the value of their creations and learning media. They instill an attitude of life and skills such as the value of cooperation, togetherness, discipline, honesty, and deliberation because there are rules that should be met by the players. Many traditional games involve body movements, songs or sounds as media, and playing tools.

Materials, processes, and functions of traditional games are also appropriate learning media are close to nature and contribute to the improvement of children's natural intelligence and personal development. This game is self-made, thus it can help children develop their creativity and sense of responsibility.

2. Research Method

The quantitative descriptive method is used to answer the problem formulation regarding the urgency and implementation of children's traditional games as ECE learning media. Data were collected by indirect interviews using a questionnaire tested for validity and reliability. The validity of each item used was tested using Pearson's Product Moment correlation. The results showed 43 items, of which 40 were declared valid, and 3 were invalid. The reliability test used is the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient technique, and the results obtained an α of 0.981, which is greater than 0.250. Therefore, the traditional game-based ECE instrument is declared reliable.

The research locations were schools in East Bandung. There were seven schools, and 62 respondents who filled out the research questionnaire. This study's respondents comprised teachers, principals/deputy principals, and owners/managers of the school/foundation. The respondents who filled out the google form questionnaire, which was distributed online, were ECE teachers, principals, deputy principals, and school owners/heads of ECE school/foundations, with details in the following table 1.

Table 1: Respondents

Category	N	%
Teacher	30	48.39
Principal/Deputy Principal	25	40.32
Foundation Owner/Foundation Management	7	11.29
TOTAL	62	100

To draw conclusions, the percentage is calculated using the following formula: $P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$. Description: P = Percentage; F = Number of points on the instrument; N = Total frequency. The results are categorized into several percentage interpretation criteria, which are as follows:

- 100% : All (A)
- 84% - 99% : Almost Entirely (AE)
- 68% - 83% : Most (M)
- 51% - 67% : More than Half (MtH)
- 50% : Half (H)
- 34% - 49% : Less than Half (LtH)
- 18% - 33% : Small Part (SP)

Furthermore, based on quantitative data, an in-depth study was conducted through observation and interviews at three schools, which have implemented traditional games and also developed new games as learning media. The ECE schools are TK Laboratorium Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia on the Cibiru Campus; TK Negeri Sadang Serang, TK Swasta Arunika Waldorf.

3. Research Results

3.1. Urgency and Implementation of Utilization of Traditional Game Wealth in Early Childhood Education Learning

To answer the first problem, the following research results explain how teachers, principals, and owners or founders of schools/foundations view the urgency of using traditional games as learning media in ECE schools.

They believe that various types of traditional games are essential to be applied in ECE learning. Furthermore, they are important to be explored and used as learning media that can improve and strengthen students' character.

Most teachers agree and strongly agree (82.40%) that traditional games can stimulate children to develop cooperative skills, help them adjust to and interact positively with one another, condition children to control themselves, develop an attitude of empathy towards friends and respect for others, improve discipline, obey the rules, and sportsmanship. Traditional games can also introduce and improve their ability to adapt to the natural environment and society, improve cognitive and intellectual abilities, increase the strength of their character and positive attitude. It also improve motor and interpersonal skills, and train children to move actively, which positively affects their health. Furthermore, traditional games increase the power of imagination and high creativity, create an atmosphere that stimulates children to learn and master skills and condition them to make choices, solve problems, communicate, and negotiate. It further instills attitudes and life skills such as the values of cooperation, togetherness, discipline, honesty, and deliberation to reach a consensus.

Furthermore, these results indicate that more than half of the principals and school owners/founders agree and strongly agree (67.80%) that traditional games can improve and strengthen various characters and skills, as mentioned above. Each type of game has different characteristics and specifications for enhancing the strength of different characters and skills. The results showed that all teachers agreed and strongly agreed that traditional games were included in the curriculum. However, no one has carried out a conceptual study, harmonized the types of traditional games with learning objectives, and included them in the curriculum.

The data shows that more than half at 51.2% of teachers include one traditional game in their lesson plans. Furthermore, 49% included more than three traditional games in their lesson plan, and 28.7 included two. It is included in the Daily Activity Plan (DAP) by only some new teachers. A small proportion of 36.7% has used more than three types of traditional games. The rest only play traditional game media of one or two types of games. When written in the DAP, not all teachers automatically play traditional game media. Eventually, only a small proportion, accounting for 23.3%, applied more than three traditional games in class and thematic learning activities. The rest only play traditional game media of one or two types.

A total of 56.7% of the teachers played *Slepdur*, 40% *Pacublek-cublek Uang*, 50% *Paciwit-Ciwit Lutung*, 60% *Oray-Orayan*, 73.4% *Hompimpah*, 43.3% *Jump Rope*, 56.7% *Cinggarispit*, 53.4% *Hahayaman*, and 50% *Sapintrong*. The following illustrates the types of Sundanese Traditional Games teachers play most often.

Table 2: Types and Benefits of Traditional Sundanese Games Often Played by Teachers

Game Name	Illustration Image	Benefits (Training and Building Character)
<i>Slepdur</i>		Wisdom Physical Strength Self-awareness Sportsmanship

Image Source: Soleh, Ridwan (2019)

Game Name	Illustration Image	Benefits (Training and Building Character)
<i>Prepet Jengkol</i>	<p data-bbox="544 566 935 595"><i>Image Source: Rozak, Abdul (2014)</i></p>	Body resistance Body balance Honesty Responsible
<i>Ayang-Ayang Gung</i>	<p data-bbox="544 884 935 913"><i>Image Source: Abah Mayana (2016)</i></p>	Togetherness Compassion Body resistance
<i>Pacublek-cublek Uang</i>	<p data-bbox="592 1294 884 1323"><i>Image Source: GWI (2015)</i></p>	Strategy Sharpness of taste Mind reading skills Mental training
<i>Ambil-ambilan</i>	<p data-bbox="512 1619 965 1648"><i>Image Source: Asep Jaenal Aripin (2020)</i></p>	Sports Physical Strength Body balance
<i>Ucang-ucang Angge</i>	<p data-bbox="480 1865 997 1930"><i>Image Source: Kata Bijak Basa Sunda (2015), www.gspradio.com (2020)</i></p>	Cooperation Sports Compassion Physical Strength Body balance

Game Name	Illustration Image	Benefits (Training and Building Character)
<p><i>Paciwit-ciwit Lutung</i></p>	<p><i>Image Source: Damisidharta (2006), misstjitjih (2020)</i></p>	<p>Feeling Awareness Togetherness Tolerance</p>
<p><i>Oray-orayan</i></p>	<p><i>Image Source: Laut, Timun (2012)</i></p>	<p>Dexterity Leadership Obedience Tolerance Skills</p>
<p><i>Hompimpah</i></p>	<p><i>Image Source: Wikipedia (2020)</i></p>	<p>Sharpness of taste Mind reading skills Mental strength</p>
<p><i>Lompat Tali</i></p>	<p><i>Image Source: Waloni, Gitta (2012)</i></p>	<p>Agility Courage Self Confidence Discipline Dexterity</p>
<p><i>Cing Ciripit</i></p>	<p><i>Image Source: Wikipedia, 2022</i></p>	<p>Counting skills Ingenuity Dexterity</p>

Game Name	Illustration Image	Benefits (Training and Building Character)
Hahayaman	<p>Image Source: https://lokalklik.com/2022</p>	Agility Cooperation and social spirit Health
Sapintrong	<p>Image Source: https://bandungnews.id/2022</p>	Agility Health Competition Courage Trust

The types of traditional games that most teachers in learning do not implement are *Ambilan-ambilan* at 46.6%, 50% *Ucang-ucang Angge*, 73.3% *Sorodot Gaplok*, 80% *Gatrik*, 76.8% *Egrang* or *Jajangkungan*, 63.3% *Bebentengan*, and 66.8% *Galah Asin* or *Gobak Sodor*.

Figure 1: Graphics of Implementation of Traditional Games in Kindergarten

The graphic above showed that most schools, accounting for 75.8%, implement *hompimpah* games, 51.6% *cingcirit*, 53.2% *hahayaman*, 58.1% *paciwit-ciwit lutung*, 62.9% *endog-endogan*, 64.5% *slepdur*, and 64.5% *oray-orayan*.

3.2. Variety of Childhood Education Learning Media Developed by Traditional Game-Based Teachers

Tafonao, Setinawati, Tari (2019) stated thae the teachers can understand the power of the media as a source of learning. The benefit of learning media is determining the quality of learning delivered by a teacher. So, in addition to applying existing traditional games, which are quite exciting and interesting, some teachers have also created

new games based on existing traditional games. Three schools apply traditional games effectively and are creative and improvisational in developing them. They include UPI Laboratory Kindergarten, Cibiru; Sadang Serang State Kindergarten; and Arunika Waldorf Private Kindergarten. This study compared, analyzed, synthesized, and develop the Syllabus and Daily Activity Plan (DAP) models using traditional game learning media in the three ECE schools. Some of the teachers' created games are *Ucing sarong*, *Simar* game, Throw the dice "Let's Follow," Chain words, Motion games, and songs.

4. Discussion

The results show that more than half of principals and school owners/founders agree and strongly agree that traditional games can enhance and strengthen various characters and skills. Similarly, Sulistyningtyas and Fauziah (2019) conclude that traditional games have many benefits in all aspects of early childhood development, including physical-motor, socio-emotional, moral, cognitive, and language development. Each type of game has different characteristics and specifications for enhancing the strength of characters and skills.

Children's play is essential for their overall development. Furthermore, traditional games are authentic learning in cultural and value inheritance (Parlebas, 2010; Ambretti, Palumbo, and Kourkoutas, 2019). Tan, Nonis, and Chan (2020) showed that all participants significantly improved their balance and motor skills after participating in traditional and unstructured free play. However, traditional game participants performed significantly better in terms of manual dexterity and overall motor skills when compared to the free playgroup.

The issue is whether the knowledge and awareness that traditional games play a significant role as learning media also result in their implementation in ECE learning practices. Conceptually, no one has studied, harmonized the types of traditional games with learning objectives, and incorporated them into the curriculum.

The data shows that more than half of teachers include one traditional game in the lesson plan, and less than half include more than three. Only a small proportion of teachers include two traditional games in the lesson plan. Similarly, it is included in the Daily Activity Plan (DAP) by only some new teachers. The rest only play traditional game media of one or two types. It turns out that only a small percentage of teachers apply more than three traditional games in class and thematic learning activities.

Sulistyningtyas and Fauziah (2019) in Yogyakarta showed that 55% of 40 ECE subject teachers often apply traditional games but are still rarely applied by 45%. This is due to teachers' limited number and level of understanding, lack of reading resources, limited facilities, and time. However, the greatest impediment is the absence of support from policymakers since teacher motivation to introduce traditional games is relatively high.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Learning using traditional game media is proven to be very important in supporting children's overall development, including cognitive, character, and motoric aspects. They are authentic learning media that pass on culture and noble values. All instructors agreeing or strongly agreeing that traditional games should be included in the curriculum is a reasonable and rational conclusion to draw from the data. However, only a few new teachers have been included in the Daily Activity Plan (DAP). When it is written in the DAP, not all teachers immediately play traditional game learning media. It turns out that only a small number of them implement more than three traditional games in class or thematic learning activities. The rest only play one or two types of traditional game learning media.

This study recommends that local governments, school administrators, and ECE proprietors incorporate these traditional games into their curricula due to their importance. Furthermore, all stakeholders should provide support in increasing teacher understanding and motivation, reading resources, learning facilities, and time. In addition, teachers must be encouraged and facilitated to develop their own learning media, namely in the form of game innovations that are packaged creatively.

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